

IN-PLANE UNSATURATED PERMEABILITY OF NATURAL FIBER MATS

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1 General Introduction

Natural fibers are increasingly being used as a replacement for more conventional fiber reinforcements due to cost savings and the environmental consideration of using renewable materials. These materials have been found to have acceptable mechanical properties, however, there is relatively little information regarding the processing characteristics of natural fiber mats.

In-plane unsaturated permeability is an essential processing value for modeling the manufacturing of composite materials [1-3]. It is a value that relates the speed that a fluid front is able to pass through a permeable media to other processing variables. Additionally, it is important to study natural fibers because of the variation present in these natural materials, and it is important to understand the effects these variations have on processing parameters [4].

2 Background

2.1 Materials

The materials examined in this study include five different nonwoven mats made from flax, hemp and kenaf fibers. All of the fiber types examined in this study are bast type fibers extracted from plants. None of the fibers from this study underwent surface treatments.

During the retting process to extract the bast fiber from the stems of the flax plant, a byproduct is created called shive. Shive consists of the woody core material from the stem. It is difficult to separate all of the shive from the flax fiber, and so it is often found in flat fiber mats in some quantity. For this study, three different flax mats are examined; a low shive content mat, a mid shive content mat, and a

high shive content mat. The hemp and kenaf mats are both considered to have low woody core content, and a single mat of each is included in this study.

2.2 Characterization

The mats were characterized by fiber density, areal density, shive (or trash) content, fiber fineness, wax content, and contact angle between simulated resin and the fiber. The fiber density was determined by the Archimedes method using canola oil as the immersion fluid. Fiber density and areal density are shown below in Table 1.

Shive content of the flax mats was determined by the Composites Innovation Centre by grinding a sample of each mat and scanning the ground shive and fiber mixture in the NIR spectrum. The shive content is then calculated from the NIR results. The shive content results are in Figure 1.

USDA CQRS conducted the tests for fiber fineness and wax content. Fiber fineness was measured recording a picture of the fiber using light microscopy, and analyzing the picture with the program Fibreshape. Wax content was found using a solvent extraction of only the fiber in the mats, shive was not included. Table 2 contains the results of the fiber fineness and wax content.

The contact angle between each simulated resin and each mat was determined to examine the wetting characteristics of the mats. The contact angle test was performed by separating individual fibers from each mat and applying a drop to the fiber. The contact angle was then measured using the First Ten Angstroms FTA 125. An image of a mid shive flax fiber during testing is shown below in Figure 2. The results of the contact angle testing are shown in Figure 3.

2.3 Permeability

Permeability is a value defined by Darcy's law

$$\mathbf{v}_D = \frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v}_D is the Darcy's velocity vector, P is the pressure, μ is the viscosity, and \mathbf{K} is the permeability tensor. When Darcy's law is combined with the continuity equation

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_D = 0 \quad (2)$$

and boundary conditions applied, an equation relating the fluid front to the conditions affecting permeability is found.

$$\Phi(\rho_f) = \tau \quad (3)$$

Φ is a function of the dimensionless fluid front, $\rho_f = r_f/r_o$, where r_f is the fluid front radius and r_o is the inlet radius. Specifically,

$$\Phi(\rho_f) = \frac{1}{4} [\rho_f^2 (2 \cdot \ln \rho_f - 1) + 1] \quad (4)$$

Permeability can then be determined by

$$\tau = \frac{k_{xye} (P_o - P_f) t}{\varepsilon \mu r_o^2} \quad (5)$$

Where k_{xye} is the isotropic in-plane permeability, P_o is the inlet pressure, P_f is the pressure at the fluid front, t is time, ε is porosity of the mat, and μ is the resin viscosity [5].

This model was chosen to evaluate the in-plane permeability of the nonwoven mats because there is no preferred direction for the fluid flow, and so the mats are considered to be quasi-isotropic in the in-plane direction. Unidirectional or woven mats exhibit anisotropic permeability behavior and require a more complex model.

3 Testing

3.1 Compression Testing

Compression testing was completed on each mat in order to determine the required pressures to achieve different fiber volume fractions during processing, as well as to observe the relaxation response of these viscoelastic mats when held under compression.

This test was executed by placing a material sample between two plates located in a load frame moving

at a constant rate of compression of 3mm/min. The samples were compressed to a thickness equivalent to a 50% fiber volume fraction, and held at that thickness for a period of 15 minutes for the total test time.

3.2 Permeability

In-plane permeability is measured using a custom apparatus where the simulated resin is injected into a hole placed at the center of the test mat. The fluid front is then observed through a transparent plate and video is recorded, and later analyzed, in order to measure the location of the fluid front at any given time. The data on the movement of the fluid front is used to determine the Darcy's velocity vector.

A pair of pressure transducers located near the fluid inlet, combined with a data acquisition system, records the simulated resin pressure throughout the test. During the test, the simulated resin is injected at a constant pressure, while the outer diameter of the test mat is exposed to the atmosphere.

The permeability apparatus is also capable of evaluating the materials at different fiber volume fractions. This is done by locating the mats between two opposing plates, and distancing the plates using a machined spacer to achieve a thickness correlated to a given fiber volume, for a given fiber mat. The permeability tests were conducted across a varying fiber volume range for each material. This was due to the varying compaction pressure for each mat and the limitations of the permeability apparatus.

The fluids used for testing were two different motor oils which have similar viscosities to liquid molding resin systems. Motor oils were used instead of resin systems due to the high cost of the resin systems, short working times, changes to viscosity as the resin system cures, and difficulty of cleanup. An SAE 40W motor oil was used to simulate a thicker resin system, and was found to have a viscosity of 400 cP. To simulate a less viscous resin system, a 10W-40 motor oil was used and it was found to have a viscosity of 220 cP.

4 Results

4.1 Compression Testing

As seen in Figure 4, all tested mats exhibited a relaxation in compaction pressure while the fiber volume was held constant. There is an approximately 20% reduction in the compaction

pressure for each mat following an approximately 12 minute relaxation period. The phenomenon was previously reported for natural fiber nonwoven mats by Mekic et al [4].

4.2 Contact Angle

Figure 3 shows the results of the contact angle testing. All of the mats except the high shive flax exhibited a higher contact angle for the higher viscosity oil. The high shive flax mat had no appreciable difference in the contact angle between the two oils. It is important to mention that contact angle was only measured on the fibers, and did not include shive.

4.2 Permeability Testing

A comparison of the permeability of the high, mid, and low shive flax mats using 220 cP simulated resin is shown in Figure 5. Shive content appears to have increased the permeability of the mats. This is likely due to the creation of localized areas of increased porosity in the areas around shive, or shive concentrations, in the mat. The shive content correlates well with permeability as seen by the comparative difference in shive content and permeability. There is a relatively small difference in shive content between the low and mid shive mats corresponding to a relatively small difference in permeability. On the other hand, there is a relatively large difference in the shive content between the low and high shive mats, corresponding to a relatively large difference in permeability between the low and high shive mats.

It is also noted that the increase in permeability due to the shive content reduces as the fiber volume fraction increases. This is likely due to a reduction in the localized porosity around the shive as the mat is compacted. Another result of the higher shive content appears to be an increased variation of the permeability, particularly in the high shive mat, as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 6 is the same plot as Figure 5 with the exception that Figure 6 is for the higher viscosity 400 cP simulated resin. The permeability for all mats exposed to the 400 cP simulated resin are very similar to those of the 220 cP simulated resin. Also of consideration is the difference in contact angle between the two simulated resins for the low and mid shive flax. Based on the similarity of the permeability for the two simulated resins, and the

contact angle testing, it is likely that the resin viscosity and contact angle do not affect the permeability as greatly as the shive content.

Figure 7 is a comparison of the permeability for the hemp, kenaf, and low shive flax mats. Of these three mats, kenaf had the highest permeability, and low shive flax had the lowest. Fiber thickness correlates well with this difference in permeability, where kenaf exhibited the highest fiber thickness, and low shive flax exhibited the lowest fiber thickness. Wax content also correlated with the difference in permeability between the three mats. Low shive flax exhibited the highest wax content and the lowest permeability, and kenaf exhibited the lowest wax content and the highest permeability.

5 Summary

Five different natural fibers mats were characterized and tested for permeability using two simulated resins. It was found that the higher viscosity oil exhibited a higher contact angle on all fibers except the high shive flax. When comparing the results of the three flax mats, the presence of shive in a natural fiber mat appears to increase the permeability, and the variation of the permeability, of the mat. The effect of shive content on permeability reduces as the fiber volume fraction is increased. The shive content also had a greater effect on permeability than simulated resin viscosity or contact angle. When the three different natural fiber types were compared, higher fiber thickness correlated with a higher permeability, and a higher wax content correlated with a lower permeability.

Table 1. Mat Density Table

Mat	Density (g/cm ³)	Areal Density (gsm)
Low Shive Flax	1.287	635
Mid Shive Flax	1.300	933
High Shive Flax	0.954	1300
Hemp	1.391	588
Kenaf	1.331	409

Table 2. Mat Properties

Mat	Fiber Thickness (μm)	Wax Content (%)
Low Shive Flax	21.78	2.12
Mid Shive Flax	30.57	1.09
High Shive Flax	30.88	0.87
Hemp	50.19	0.53
Kenaf	61.87	0.32

Fig. 1. Measured shive content for the three tested flax fiber mats with standard deviation.

Figure 2. Contact angle measurement for a mid shive flax fiber with 220 cP oil.

Figure 3. Contact angle results with standard deviation.

Fig. 4. Compression test results for all fiber mats.

Figure 5. Premeability comparison of flax mats with varying shive content using 220 cP oil.

Figure 6. Premeability comparison of flax mats with varying shive content using 400 cP oil.

Figure 7. Permeability comparison of various mats with 220 cP oil.

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